

Online Educational Resources Library

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Sportshealth
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TITLE	LINK	TYPE OF RESOURCE	AUTORS HIP	LICENCE	LANGUAGE
Body painting anatomy (some examples)	https://www.shutterstock.com/es/image-photo/human-upper-leg-anatomy-sketch-on-591335378	Image	created by others	Copyright	English
Top 10 facts about sport & health	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mnus52QM3TCLMLcxmowivGoleVH1i_Kt/view?usp=share_link	PDF	Self-authorship	Other	English
Technology biomechanics activity	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1J7-EN3yvza0cumbbQyDv0WJbuszrnJli/edit?usp=sharing&oid=112761443414545542982&rtpof=true&sd=true	Other	created by others	Copyright	Spanish
Working levers with Scratch program	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1OXf3fV-i0oZ6tt4J6MTL4N1QcX7iaC1f/edit?usp=sharing&oid=112761443414545542982&rtpof=true&sd=true	Other	created by others	Copyright	Spanish
Anatomy Body Painting - Faculty of Health	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nR5FqLissEc	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
Open Office statistical manual	https://wiki.openoffice.org/wiki/Documentation/How_Tos/Calc:_Statistical_functions	Other	created by others	Copyright	English
Maths rubric	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1tQFEohrbJlksbSiab0i1w4OREtabelA/view?usp=sharing	PDF	Self-authorship	Copyright	English
Correlation graph in Open Office video	https://youtu.be/7RjZOMsht5k?si=LDgKTSbbTxXMF_Oy	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
Importance of physical activity	https://youtu.be/UzWd8ynGLEM?si=ytfTDIQR2rokJ90k	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
Exercise article	https://www.partnermd.com/blog/30-minutes-of-exercise-can-reduce-risk-major-diseases	Other	created by others	Copyright	English
What happens inside your body	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wWGuLlAa000	Video	created by others	Copyright	English

when you exercise?					
Top 10 sport & health facts	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mnus52QM3TCLMLcxmowivGoleVH1i_Kt/view?usp=sharing	PDF	Self-authorship	Other	English

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